

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series. Part X. The Mode of Ring Opening of the Anhydrides of 1-Carboxy Cycloalkane-1-Acetic Acids During the Friedel-Crafts Reaction

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The anhydrides of 1-carboxy cycloalkane-1-acetic acids on treatment with dry methanol furnish the half acid-esters of the type III; these are converted into their acid chlorides and later condensed with benzene to give the keto-acids of the type II obtained by the direct condensation of the anhydrides with benzene.

IN order to determine the mode of opening of the ring of the anhydrides of 1-carboxy cycloalkane-1-acetic acids of the type I during Friedel-Crafts reaction and to substantiate the structures of the keto-acids of the type II ($R = H$) obtained by the condensation of the aromatic hydrocarbons with the above anhydrides, the anhydrides of the cis- and trans-forms of 1-carboxy 4-, and trans-2-methyl-cyclohexane-1-acetic acids, 1-carboxy cyclopentane-, cyclohexane-, and cycloheptane 1-acetic acids were refluxed with dry methanol and the half-acid esters were assigned the structure III, which was different from the one suggested by Bardhan¹, and Qudrat-i-Khuda and Bhattacharya².

The former author treated the anhydride (I; $n = 4$) and the latter workers (I; $n = 5$) with dry methanol and obtained the corresponding half-acid ester to which both had assigned the structure IV ($n = 4$ or 5).

The half acid-ester obtained from the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclohexane-1-acetic acid was obtained as a liquid (Table 1), which in spite of a number of repetitions, never solidified in our hands; Qudrat-i-Khuda and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*) report its m.p. 57° which

may be the unchanged anhydride, m.p. 60°. This half acid-ester was converted into its acid chloride, b.p. 130°/8 mm; IR spectra (1795 and 1730 cm^{-1}) and elemental analysis (Found: C, 54.8; H, 6.8; Cl, 16.0. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires C, 54.9; H, 6.8; Cl, 16.2%) confirmed it to be the ester acid chloride and not the anhydride.

All the acid chlorides ($n = 4, 5$ and 6) were then individually condensed with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give the products of the type II ($R = \text{CH}_3$) which on hydrolysis furnished the corresponding keto-acids of the type II ($R = H$) having m.p.s. identical with those obtained by the direct condensation of the corresponding anhydrides with benzene. All these keto-acids formed pyrylium salts thereby confirming the structure II; if the half acid ester had the structure IV, its acid chloride on Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene would give a keto acid which would not form pyrylium salt. Further confirmation in support of our work is given by the work of Rothstein and Saboor³, according to which it is not possible to obtain a ketone or a keto-acid by Friedel-Crafts reaction with anhydrides or acid chlorides of tertiary acids. On this basis we assign structure III for the half acid esters, thereby setting aside the structure IV suggested by Bardhan (*loc. cit.*) and Qudrat-i-Khuda and Bhattacharya (*loc. cit.*).

We are also supported in our findings by the work of Edwards Jr. and Sibille⁴, who have shown that during the acylation of benzene with mixed carboxylic anhydrides, the ketone formed in greater proportion is the one whose alkyl group is more strongly electron releasing in the actual non-aqueous system in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

Further confirmation for this structure is forthcoming by the recent work of Saharia and Tyagi⁵ who have carried out similar type of ring opening of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclo-octane-1-acetic

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acid (I; $n = 7$) with methanol and assigned the structure (III; $n = 7$) to the half-acid ester.

Experimental

1-Carbomethoxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid

The anhydride of trans-1-carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid m.p. 173° (5.46 g) was dissolved in dry methanol (25 ml) and the contents refluxed for 30 hr. Excess of methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue taken up in ether, the ethereal layer washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%; 4×50 ml). The alkaline solution was acidified, extracted with ether (4×75 ml), ethereal layer washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether recovered. The residue on keeping in vacuum for 24 hr solidified and had m.p. $90-1^\circ$; on two crystallisations from pet. ether ($60-80^\circ$), 1-carbomethoxy 4-

methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid was obtained in colourless needles, m.p. 95° . (Yield : 2.6 g; 40.5%). Mixed m.p. with the anhydride m.p. 107° was depressed to $73-4^\circ$. (Found : C, 61.6; H, 8.2. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 61.7; H, 8.4%). IR $\gamma_{\text{max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1742, 1710 cm^{-1} . The ethereal layer after the removal of the above half-acid ester furnished the unreacted anhydride (2.5 g).

The other half acid esters similarly prepared are given in Table 1.

Methyl β -benzoyl- α -4'-methylcyclohexyl propionate

1-Carbomethoxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (2.14 g; 0.01 mol) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (6 ml) for 6 hr, excess of thionyl chloride removed under reduced pressure, the residue dissolved in dry benzene (20 ml), cooled in ice-salt bath and anhydrous

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Half-acid ester	M.P./b.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	Yield %	Ref. Index	Mol. formula	Found(%)		Requires(%)		I.R.
						C	H	C	H	
1.	1-Carbomethoxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (cis).	67	46.7	—	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$	61.5	8.5	61.7	8.4	γ Nujol max 1742, 1710 cm^{-1}
2.	1-Carbomethoxy 2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (trans)	103	62.3	—	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$	61.8	8.2	61.7	8.4	„
3.	1-Carbomethoxy cyclohexane-1-acetic acid	175/14 mm.	41.7	n_D^{22} 1.4778	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	60.2	8.1	60.0	8.0	„
4.	1-Carbomethoxy cyclopentane-1-acetic acid	80	60.5	—	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$	58.0	7.5	58.1	7.5	„
5.	1-Carbomethoxy cycloheptane-1-acetic acid.	154-5/14 mm.	60.7	n_D^{21} 1.4853	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	61.5	8.5	61.7	8.4	„

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Name	B.P. $^\circ\text{C}$	Ref. Index	Yield (%)	Mol. formula	Found(%)		Requires(%)		I.R.
						C	H	C	H	
1.	Methyl β -benzoyl- α -4'-methylcyclohexyl-propionate (cis)	120/2 mm	n_D^{18} 1.5428	91.2	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$	74.6	8.2	74.5	8.0	γ Film max 1742, 1700 cm^{-1}
2.	Methyl β -benzoyl- α -2'-methylcyclohexyl propionate (trans)	150/7 mm	n_D^{28} 1.5620	83.9	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$	74.6	7.9	74.5	8.0	„
3.	Methyl β -benzoyl- α -cyclohexyl propionate	165/2 mm	n_D^{30} 1.5670	77.0	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$	73.6	7.6	73.8	7.7	„
4.	Methyl β -benzoyl- α -cyclopentyl propionate	134-5/10 mm	n_D^{32} 1.5565	73.2	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$	73.0	7.2	73.2	7.3	„
5.	Methyl β -benzoyl- α -cycloheptyl propionate.	120/5 mm	n_D^{29} 1.5305	73.0	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$	74.5	8.2	74.5	8.0	„

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	Name	M.P. °C	Mixed m.p. with the keto acid, obtained by direct condensation of the corresponding anhydride with benzene °C	Mol. formula	Found(%)		Requires(%)		I.R.
					C	H	C	H	
1.	β -Benzoyl- α -4'-methyl cyclohexyl propionic acid (cis)	144	144	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃	73.6	7.7	73.8	7.7	γ Nujol max 1710, 1690 cm ⁻¹
2.	β -Benzoyl- α -2'-methyl cyclohexyl propionic acid (trans)	144	144	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃	73.4	7.6	73.8	7.7	„
3.	β -Benzoyl- α -cyclohexyl propionic acid	117	117	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₃	73.0	7.4	73.2	7.3	„
4.	β -Benzoyl- α -cyclopentyl propionic acid	168	168	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃	72.3	6.7	72.4	6.9	„
5.	β -Benzoyl- α -cycloheptyl propionic acid	145	145	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃	73.6	7.5	73.8	7.7	„

aluminium chloride (1.47 g; 0.011 mol) added in small lots with vigorous shaking. The reaction mixture after keeping in an ice-salt bath for 2 hr was left at room temperature for 24 hr. The contents were heated in an oil bath (50–60°) for 2 hr, the complex worked up in the normal manner and methyl- β -benzoyl- α -4'-methylcyclohexyl propionate had b.p. 125°/2.5 mm. $n_D^{29.5}$ 1.5178. (Yield: 2.0 g; 73%). (Found: C, 74.4; H, 8.2. C₁₇H₂₂O₃ requires C, 74.5; H, 8.0%). IR γ_{max}^{film} 1742, 1700 cm⁻¹.

Other esters prepared in an identical manner are listed in Table 2.

β -Benzoyl- α -4'-methylcyclohexyl propionic acid

Methyl β -benzoyl- α -4'-methylcyclohexylpropionate (1.37 g) was refluxed with ethanolic potassium hydroxide (20%; 100 ml) for 20 hr, excess of ethanol removed under reduced pressure, the residue poured on to crushed ice, acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%; 4 × 50 ml), the alkaline extract on acidification

with concentrated hydrochloric acid deposited the acid, m.p. 159–160°. On crystallisation from benzene-petrol (60–80°), β -benzoyl- α -4'-methylcyclohexyl propionic acid was obtained in colourless needles, m.p. 165°. Mixed m.p. with the keto-acid obtained by the direct condensation of the anhydride of trans-1-carboxy 4-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, m.p. 173° with benzene in the ratios (1:1) and (1:2) recorded no depression.

Other propionic acids prepared in an identical manner are entered in Table 3.

References

1. J. C. BARDHAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2591, 2684.
2. M. QUDRAT-I-KHUDA AND K. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 15.
3. E. ROTHSTEIN and M. A. SABOOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 425.
4. W. R. EDWARDS, JR. and E. C. SIBILLE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, 28, 674.
5. G. S. SAHARIA and M. P. TYAGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 467.